

Let There
be Light

THEIA:
*Next-generation
neutrino
detection*

Gabriel D. Orebi Gann
UC Berkeley & LBNL
NuPhys 2026

Innovative neutrino detection

Combine two well-tested methods for neutrino detection, for enhanced precision:

Cherenkov light

- Emitted with a unique topology that preserves directional information
- Particle-dependent threshold

Scintillation light

- Extremely high light yield: high efficiency for detection
- Particle-dependent response offers particle identification

Innovative neutrino detection

Combine two well-tested methods for neutrino detection, for enhanced precision:

Cherenkov light

- Emitted with a unique topology that preserves directional information
- Particle-dependent threshold

Scintillation light

- Extremely high light yield: high efficiency for detection
- Particle-dependent response offers particle identification

The whole is greater than the sum of the parts

*The ratio of the two signals provides additional information on the type of particle interacting:
Improved background rejection for precision measurements*

Innovative neutrino detection

Combine two well-tested methods for neutrino detection, for enhanced precision:

Cherenkov light

- Emitted with a unique topology that preserves directional information
- Particle-dependent threshold

Scintillation light

- Extremely high light yield: high efficiency for detection
- Particle-dependent response offers particle identification

The whole is greater than the sum of the parts

The ratio of the two signals provides additional information on the type of particle interacting:
Improved background rejection for precision measurements

Challenging technical goal: preserve directional Cherenkov signature against more abundant scintillation yield

Innovative neutrino detection

Combine two well-tested methods for neutrino detection, for enhanced precision:

Cherenkov light

- Emitted with a unique topology that preserves directional information
- Particle-dependent threshold

Scintillation light

- Extremely high light yield: high efficiency for detection
- Particle-dependent response offers particle identification

The whole is greater than the sum of the parts

The ratio of the two signals provides additional information on the type of particle interacting:
Improved background rejection for precision measurements

Challenging technical goal: preserve directional Cherenkov signature against more abundant scintillation yield

Innovative neutrino detection

Combine two well-tested methods for neutrino detection, for enhanced precision:

Cherenkov light

- Emitted with a unique topology that preserves directional information
- Particle-dependent threshold

Scintillation light

- Extremely high light yield: high efficiency for detection
- Particle-dependent response offers particle identification

The whole is greater than the sum of the parts

The ratio of the two signals provides additional information on the type of particle interacting:
Improved background rejection for precision measurements

Challenging technical goal: preserve directional Cherenkov signature against more abundant scintillation yield

1 GeV
 μ^-

Long Wavelengths ($t_{\text{resid}} < 3.0$ ns)

1 GeV
 μ^-

Short Wavelengths (All)

2-for-1

Pure LS +
dichroicons

Credit: Sam Young, Penn

Cherenkov

Scintillation

1 GeV
 e^-

Long Wavelengths ($t_{resid} < 3.0$ ns)

1 GeV
 e^-

Short Wavelengths (All)

2-for-1

Credit: Sam Young, Penn

Cherenkov

Scintillation

THEIA

THEIA

THEIA

The Goddess THEIA

The THEIA collection was created to bring out a women's inner goddess

THEIA Detector Concept

THEIA

- Large-scale detector (25+ kton) in a new, dedicated cavern
- Novel LS target e.g. WbLS, slow LS
- High coverage with fast, high-efficiency, spectrally-sensitive photon detectors
- Deep underground (4800–6800 mwe)
- Isotope loading (Gd, Te, Li...)
- Flexible — target, loading, configuration
- **Broad physics program**

White paper - Eur. Phys. J. C 80, 416 (2020)

THEIA

- Large-scale detector (25+ kton) in a new, dedicated cavern
- Novel LS target e.g. WbLS, slow LS
- High coverage with fast, high-efficiency, spectrally-sensitive photon detectors
- Deep underground (4800–6800 mwe)
- Isotope loading (Gd, Te, Li...)
- Flexible — target, loading, configuration
- **Broad physics program**

White paper - Eur. Phys. J. C 80, 416 (2020)

Theia Physics Program

THEIA physics program

Neutrinos as a probe of nature

THEIA physics program

Neutrinos as a probe of nature

Studying the fundamental nature of matter

THEIA physics program

Neutrinos as a probe of nature

Particle astrophysics

Studying the fundamental nature of matter

THEIA physics program

Neutrinos as a probe of nature

Particle astrophysics

Nuclear physics

Studying the fundamental nature of matter

THEIA physics program

Neutrinos as a probe of nature

Particle
astrophysics

Nuclear physics

Studying the fundamental nature of matter

High energy physics

THEIA physics program

Neutrinos as a probe of nature

Physics over 5 orders of magnitude

Particle astrophysics

Nuclear physics

Studying the fundamental nature of matter

High energy physics

THEIA physics program

Neutrinos as a probe of nature

Physics over 5 orders of magnitude

Particle astrophysics

Nuclear physics

Studying the fundamental nature of matter

High energy physics

Remarkably, the same detector could show that neutrinos and antineutrinos are the same, **and** that “neutrinos” and “antineutrinos” oscillate differently

THEIA physics program

Neutrinos as a probe of nature

Physics over 5 orders of magnitude

Particle astrophysics

Nuclear physics

Studying the fundamental nature of matter

High energy physics

Remarkably, the same detector could show that neutrinos and antineutrinos are the same, **and** that “neutrinos” and “antineutrinos” oscillate differently

Matter-dominated universe

Solar neutrinos

- Unique few-% level sensitivity to CNO ν
- Unique probe of matter effect / matter-vacuum transition
- Precision pp: luminosity, understand solar energy production
- Potential Li loading for CC (Haxton)

Solar neutrinos

- Unique few-% level sensitivity to CNO ν
- Unique probe of matter effect / matter-vacuum transition
- Precision pp: luminosity, understand solar energy production
- Potential Li loading for CC (Haxton)

CNO measurement precision

Solar neutrinos

- Unique few-% level sensitivity to CNO ν
- Unique probe of matter effect / matter-vacuum transition
- Precision pp: luminosity, understand solar energy production
- Potential Li loading for CC (Haxton)

CNO measurement precision

MSW transition region

Diffuse Supernova ν Background

- Diffuse ν “glow” from past core-collapse supernovae, astrophysics of SNe
- Signature: IBD detection of antineutrino signal
- Cherenkov/scintillation ratio + ring-counting: powerful handle for background discrimination
- 5σ in 125 kton-yrs

Diffuse Supernova ν Background

- Diffuse ν “glow” from past core-collapse supernovae, astrophysics of SNe
- Signature: IBD detection of antineutrino signal
- Cherenkov/scintillation ratio + ring-counting: powerful handle for background discrimination
- 5σ in 125 kton-yrs

SK-GD likely to find first evidence of DSNB
Background limited
Low threshold critical to extract much of the science

Anti- ν Detection

- **Geo- ν** observation by KL, Borexino, SNO+ (07-2025!)
- **THEIA**: large statistics, complementary site
- Annual rate equivalent to current global data set
 - Full spectral analysis with BDT for bkg rejection
 - Future improvements: PID (p/e+, e-/e+)
- Could offer first evidence for surface variation
- U/Th ratio to 15% precision in 10 years

Anti- ν Detection

- **Geo- ν** observation by KL, Borexino, SNO+ (07-2025!)
- **THEIA**: large statistics, complementary site
- Annual rate equivalent to current global data set
 - Full spectral analysis with BDT for bkg rejection
 - Future improvements: PID (p/e+, e-/e+)
- Could offer first evidence for surface variation
- U/Th ratio to 15% precision in 10 years
- **Reactor ν** prospects: ~ 20 reactor ev/kt-yr
 - Demonstrate techniques for remote reactor monitoring
 - Precision reactor oscillation parameters
- Range & direction at >200 km standoff

$0\nu\beta\beta$ with THEIA

1. Demonstrated low internal backgrounds & particle ID capabilities
2. Massive detector allows fiducialization from external backgrounds
3. Many backgrounds measured prior to isotope loading
4. Isotope can be scaled, removed, enriched, or depleted from the detector to allow in-situ confirmation of signal
5. Leverages significant R&D and experience from SNO+, KamLAND-Zen, Borexino, etc.

$0\nu\beta\beta$ with THEIA

1. Demonstrated low internal backgrounds & particle ID capabilities
2. Massive detector allows fiducialization from external backgrounds
3. Many backgrounds measured prior to isotope loading
4. Isotope can be scaled, removed, enriched, or depleted from the detector to allow in-situ confirmation of signal
5. Leverages significant R&D and experience from SNO+, KamLAND-Zen, Borexino, etc.

Background reduction via event imaging: PID, multi-site, directionality

Balloon for $0\nu\beta\beta$ isotope loaded liquid scintillator

25-100 kton hybrid optical neutrino detector
 8-m radius balloon with high-LY LS and isotope
 7-m fiducial, 3% $^{\text{nat}}\text{Te}$ (or $^{\text{enr}}\text{Xe}$), 10 years

$0\nu\beta\beta$ with THEIA

1. Demonstrated low internal backgrounds & particle ID capabilities
2. Massive detector allows fiducialization from external backgrounds
3. Many backgrounds measured prior to isotope loading
4. Isotope can be scaled, removed, enriched, or depleted from the detector to allow in-situ confirmation of signal
5. Leverages significant R&D and experience from SNO+, KamLAND-Zen, Borexino, etc.

Background reduction via event imaging: PID, multi-site, directionality

25-100 kton hybrid optical neutrino detector
 8-m radius balloon with high-LY LS and isotope
 7-m fiducial, 3% $^{\text{nat}}\text{Te}$ (or $^{\text{enr}}\text{Xe}$), 10 years

$0\nu\beta\beta$ with THEIA

1. Demonstrated low internal backgrounds & particle ID capabilities
2. Massive detector allows fiducialization from external backgrounds
3. Many backgrounds measured prior to isotope loading
4. Isotope can be scaled, removed, enriched, or depleted from the detector to allow in-situ confirmation of signal
5. Leverages significant R&D and experience from SNO+, KamLAND-Zen, Borexino, etc.

Background reduction via event imaging: PID, multi-site, directionality

Significant room for further optimization!

25-100 kton hybrid optical neutrino detector
 8-m radius balloon with high-LY LS and isotope
 7-m fiducial, 3% $^{\text{nat}}\text{Te}$ (or $^{\text{enr}}\text{Xe}$), 10 years

Physics reach

Primary physics goal	Reach	Context
Nucleon decay $p \rightarrow \nu K^+ (\rightarrow 3\nu)$	$T > 1.1 \times 10^{34}$ year. ($T > 1.2 \times 10^{32}$ year)	Complementary to DUNE, HK, JUNO (sensitive to different modes)
Supernova burst	$< 2^\circ$ pointing 5K events (10 kpc)	Complementary to DUNE (nu vs anti-nu) Improved flavour separation via Cher/scint
Diffuse Supernova Neutrino Background	5σ in 5 yrs	Beyond SK / JUNO due to low threshold, bkg tagging
CNO neutrinos	< 12 (2) % Wb(LS)	No concurrent competition
MSW transition	5σ	Unique handle on bkg rejection via directionality
Geoneutrinos	< 5 % (2% stats)	First high-stats measurement in North America
$0\nu\nu\beta$	$T_{1/2} > 1.1 \times 10^{28}$ year (90% C.L.)	Beyond ton-scale (further optimization possible)

Theia as a DUNE module in Phase II

Long-baseline sensitivity comparable to a LAr DUNE module

Complementary supernova sensitivity (primarily anti- ν , fast response: can act as trigger)

+ broad (new!) additional physics program

- DUNE Phase II formal process includes Theia as 1 of 3 options
- Theia is technically mature, and brings a broad physics program beyond any alternative (LAr) tech.
- Strong international team actively engaged
- Current R&D support from HEP, NNSA; LDRD at BNL to study ND requirements
- Technical demonstrators underway (BNL 30t, Eos @ LBL, ANNIE, BUTTON)

THEIA sensitivity using DUNE tools

- Same analysis framework and systematic uncertainties as official DUNE results (CAFAna)
 - Same flux uncertainty model
 - Same cross section model nuisance parameters (O vs Ar)
 - Comparably sized detector uncertainties (based on Super-K experience)
- Still using pure water phase
 - Development of scintillation + Cherenkov reconstruction is nearly complete
 - CP violation and mass ordering
 - Comparable performance to equivalent liquid argon TPC
 - Independent systematics
 - Cross-check of DUNE / HyperK

Community planning

Snowmass Neutrino Frontier

- *NF: Detectors: one of 5 priorities for development*
- *NF: Long-term outlook also BSM, terrestrial & astrophysical nu*

- **Pursuit of hybrid Cherenkov/scintillation Detectors:** Many different technologies are being developed for these, including water-based liquid scintillator, slow fluors, fast timing with LAPPDs and other devices, and spectral photon sorting with dichroicons. At very large scales like the proposed **Theia** detector, these could have very broad physics programs.

ordering region. These next-generation LAr detector ideas go by different names, such as “SLoMo”, “SoLAr”, and “LArXe.” Another idea is the proposed **Theia** detector, which is a hybrid Cherenkov/scintillation detector that could do precision measurements of very low-energy solar neutrinos, diffuse supernova neutrino detection, perform searches for sterile neutrinos, and also push well beyond DUNE in precision tests of the three-flavor mixing model (including, for example, studies of the second oscillation maximum). On the low-threshold side, much will depend on what the

Snowmass Instrumentation Frontier

- *IF: Going beyond DUNE also photon detectors & spectral sorting*

Of particular community interest is the development of hybrid Cherenkov-scintillation detectors, which can simultaneously exploit the advantages of Cherenkov light’s reconstruction of direction and related high-energy particle identification (PID) and the advantages of scintillation light, high light-yield, low-threshold detection with low-energy PID. Hybrid Cherenkov-scintillation detectors could have an exceptionally broad dynamic range in a single experiment, allowing them to have both high-energy, accelerator-based sensitivity while also achieving a broad low-energy neutrino physics and astrophysics program. Recently the Borexino

NP LRP - Fundamental Symmetries, Neutrons, and Neutrinos Whitepaper

Among possible beyond-ton-scale experiments are: NEXT, which will employ high pressure xenon gas time projection chambers with barium tagging; **THEIA**, a large-scale hybrid Cherenkov/scintillation detector that will be an outgrowth of the SNO+ and KamLAND-Zen experiments; Selena, which will employ high-

THEIA community

White paper - Eur. Phys. J. C 80, 416 & arXiv:2202.12839 [hep-ex]

- THEIA consortium: 117 authors, 48 institutions,
- Authors of THEIA White Paper:
 - 35+ institutions
 - 8 countries (CA, CN, DE, FI, IT, KR, UK, US)
- Effort embedded in international R&D programs like DRD2, RDC9
- Main experimental effort & demonstrator development:
 - ANNIE WbLS+LAPPDs, GeV reco
 - BNL-IT/30T WbLS circulation/purification
 - BUTTON low-background WbLS
 - EOS MeV reco with WbLS/slow LS
- + Large international community working on bench-top

The path to THEIA

Building on a broad program of bench-top scale development

The path to THEIA

ANNIE: 365 kg

High-energy event reconstruction, neutrino detection, LAPPDs

Building on a broad program of bench-top scale development

The path to THEIA

ANNIE: 365 kg

High-energy event reconstruction, neutrino detection, LAPPDs

Building on a broad program of bench-top scale development

BNL: 1- and 30-ton

Deployment, purification, recirculation, transparency

The path to THEIA

ANNIE: 365 kg

High-energy event reconstruction, neutrino detection, LAPPDs

Building on a broad program of bench-top scale development

BNL: 1- and 30-ton

Deployment, purification, recirculation, transparency

NuDot: 1 ton

Isotope loading, NLDBD topology

The path to THEIA

ANNIE: 365 kg

High-energy event reconstruction, neutrino detection, LAPPDs

Building on a broad program of bench-top scale development

BUTTON: 30 ton

Underground deployment, low bkg verification

BNL: 1- and 30-ton

Deployment, purification, recirculation, transparency

NuDot: 1 ton

Isotope loading, NLDBD topology

The path to THEIA

Recent progress

- Two potential host sites:
 - SURF — offers full program of CPV + low energy physics
 - SNOLAB — focus on low-energy physics
 - GATEWAY-0 approval at SNOLAB (Aug'25)
 - Requires new cavern (15-yr facs/op plan)
- New Theia working groups
 - [Long baseline: Mike Wilking, UMn]
 - Simulations — James Shen [Penn], Johann Martyn [Mainz]
 - Low-energy physics — Tanner Kaptanoglu [Berkeley], Valentina Lozza [LIP]
- *Probing the normal hierarchy of neutrinos masses with Theia*

Summary

- **Hybrid Cherenkov/ scintillation detector**
- **Multi-messenger astrophysics**
- **Probe the fundamental nature of matter: CPV and Majorana ν**
- **Technological developments have evolved from bench-top to fully integrated demonstrators**
- ***Exciting physics to come!***

Acknowledgements

This work was performed under the auspices of the U.S. Department of Energy by Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory under Contract DE-AC02-05CHI1231. The project was funded by the U.S. Department of Energy, National Nuclear Security Administration, Office of Defense Nuclear Nonproliferation Research and Development (DNN R&D) (FY19, FY20-24). This material is based upon work supported by the U.S. Department of Energy, Office of Science, Office of High Energy Physics, under Award Number DE-SC0018974 (FY18-20). This work was funded in-part by the Consortium for Monitoring, Technology, and Verification under Department of Energy National Nuclear Security Administration award number DE-NA0003920 (FY20-24), and the Nuclear Science and Security Consortium under Award Number DE-NA0003180 (FY19-20).

Thank you!

Non-comprehensive list of citations

- **Physics**

- Eur. Phys. Jour. C (2018) 78: 435
<https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-018-5925-7>
- Eur. Phys. Jour. C (2020) 80:418
<https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-020-7977-8>
- arXiv:2202.12839 [hep-ex]
- Eur. Phys. Jour. C 82 (2022) 12, 1151
<https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-022-11106-1>
- Phys. Rev. D 103, 052004 (2021)
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.103.052004>
- NIMA 943 (2019) 162420
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2019.162420>
- JINST 9 (2014) P06012
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/9/06/P06012>
- <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1409.5864>

- **Photon detection**

- <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2203.07479>
- <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1603.01843>
- NIMA 958 (2020) 162834
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2019.162834>
- JINST 19 (2024) P02032
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/19/02/P02032>

- **Scintillator development / studies**

- Phys. Rev. D 105 (2022) 9
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.105.092006>
- NIMA 972 (2020) 164106
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2020.164106>
- Materials Advances, 1 (2020) 71 - 76
<https://doi.org/10.1039/D0MA00055H>
- Eur. Phys. Jour. C (2023) 83:134
<https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-023-11242-2>
- <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.01100>
- JINST 16 (2021) P05009
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/16/05/P05009>
- NIMA 925 (2019) 1
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2019.01.014>
- Astro.Part. Phys. 109 (2019) 33
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.astropartphys.2019.02.00>
- J. Phys. G: Nucl. Part. Phys. 43 (2016) 093001.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/0954-3899/43/9/093001>
- NIMA 830 (2016) 303
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nima.2016.05.132>
- JINST 10 (2015) P12009
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/10/12/P12009>
- <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2405.05743>

- **Technology demonstrators**

- JINST 18 (2023) P02009
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/18/02/P02009>
- Phys. Rev. D 109 (2024) 072002
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.109.072002>
- JINST 19 (2024) 05, P05070.
<https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/19/05/P05070>
- <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2403.13231>
- Phys. Rev. C 95, 055801 (2017)
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevC.95.055801>
- Eur. Phys. J. C (2017) 77: 811
<https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-017-5380-x>
- Eur. Phys. J. C 80, 867 (2020)
<https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-020-8418-4>
- Eur. Phys. J. C 82-2 (2022) 169
<https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-022-10087-5>
- Eur. Phys. Jour. C (2023) 83:1094
<https://doi.org/10.1140/epjc/s10052-023-12278-0>
- Phys. Rev. D 105 (2022) 7
<https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevD.105.072003>
- <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.09293>

References

- Evidence of Antineutrinos from Distant Reactors Using Pure Water at SNO+, A. Allega et al. (The SNO+ Collaboration), Phys. Rev. Lett. 130, 091801 – Published 1 March 2023
<https://journals.aps.org/prl/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevLett.130.091801>
- Reactor on-off antineutrino measurement with KamLAND, A. Gando et al. (KamLAND Collaboration), Phys. Rev. D 88, 033001 – Published 2 August 2013
<https://journals.aps.org/prd/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevD.88.033001>
- Double Chooz θ_{13} measurement via total neutron capture detection, The Double Chooz Collaboration, Nature Physics volume 16, pages 558–564 (2020)
<https://www.nature.com/articles/s41567-020-0831-y>
- Fuel-Composition Dependent Reactor Antineutrino Yield at RENO, G. Bak et al. (RENO Collaboration), Phys. Rev. Lett. 122, 232501 – Published 12 June 2019
<https://journals.aps.org/prl/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevLett.122.232501>
- Evolution of the Reactor Antineutrino Flux and Spectrum at Daya Bay, F. P. An et al. (Daya Bay Collaboration), Phys. Rev. Lett. 118, 251801 – Published 19 June 2017
<https://journals.aps.org/prl/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevLett.118.251801>
- Improved Measurement of the Evolution of the Reactor Antineutrino Flux and Spectrum at Daya Bay, F. P. An et al. (Daya Bay Collaboration), Phys. Rev. Lett. 130, 211801 – Published 22 May 2023
<https://journals.aps.org/prl/abstract/10.1103/PhysRevLett.130.211801>

Backup

EOS @ SNS (ORNL)

- SNS provides both neutrinos and anti neutrinos
- Detection of Inverse Beta Decay: relevant for reactors
- Detection of Elastic Scattering events: directionality “holy grail”
- Neutron studies: evaluate background rejection
- Possible space identified at ORNL
- Additional technology development opportunity:
 - ▶ Li-loaded WbLS (5% organic, 10% Li)
 - ▶ Enhanced ν_e detection : CC on ${}^7\text{Li}$, spectral precision
- Supernova-relevant demonstration
- Beyond-SM searches

Channel	Rate at 20m Standoff (ev/yr)
$\nu_e e$ ES	136.89
$\nu_\mu e$ ES	20.89
$\bar{\nu}_\mu e$ ES	22.48
ν_e - ${}^7\text{Li}$ CC	533.30
ν_e - ${}^{16}\text{O}$ CC	459.34
ν_e - ${}^{12}\text{C}$ CC	37.08

event rates expected for 4 tons of LiWbLS

ν flux at SNS

neutrino cross-sections in LiWbLS

possible site for EOS deployment

Nonproliferation applications

Three-lab study of nonproliferation applications for novel neutrino detection technology (LLNL, BNL, LBNL):

- Test site transparency (TST)
- Small modular reactors (SMR)
- AUKUS / Maritime use of nuclear vessels

Nonproliferation applications

Three-lab study of nonproliferation applications for novel neutrino detection technology (LLNL, BNL, LBNL):

- Test site transparency (TST)
- Small modular reactors (SMR)
- AUKUS / Maritime use of nuclear vessels

Approach:

- Analytic calculation of signal rates
- Empirical treatment of cosmogenic backgrounds
- Analytical model for detector response to evaluate signal efficiency and accidental background rates
- Predict precision for a power measurement / sensitivity for signal detection

Nonproliferation applications

Three-lab study of nonproliferation applications for novel neutrino detection technology (LLNL, BNL, LBNL):

- Test site transparency (TST)
- Small modular reactors (SMR)
- AUKUS / Maritime use of nuclear vessels

Approach:

- Analytic calculation of signal rates
- Empirical treatment of cosmogenic backgrounds
- Analytical model for detector response to evaluate signal efficiency and accidental background rates
- Predict precision for a power measurement / sensitivity for signal detection

TST: 3σ
detection of
explosion

Nonproliferation applications

Three-lab study of nonproliferation applications for novel neutrino detection technology (LLNL, BNL, LBNL):

- Test site transparency (TST)
- Small modular reactors (SMR)
- AUKUS / Maritime use of nuclear vessels

Approach:

- Analytic calculation of signal rates
- Empirical treatment of cosmogenic backgrounds
- Analytical model for detector response to evaluate signal efficiency and accidental background rates
- Predict precision for a power measurement / sensitivity for signal detection

TST: 3σ detection of explosion

SMR: 2σ power measurement in 1 day, 20 mwe depth

Nonproliferation applications

Three-lab study of nonproliferation applications for novel neutrino detection technology (LLNL, BNL, LBNL):

- Test site transparency (TST)
- Small modular reactors (SMR)
- AUKUS / Maritime use of nuclear vessels

Approach:

- Analytic calculation of signal rates
- Empirical treatment of cosmogenic backgrounds
- Analytical model for detector response to evaluate signal efficiency and accidental background rates
- Predict precision for a power measurement / sensitivity for signal detection

TST: 3σ detection of explosion

Detection of nuclear yield in TNT equivalent

Single day power measurement of a single SMR with 95% statistical confidence

SMR: 2σ power measurement in 1 day, 20 mwe depth

Reactor core power measurements to 99% statistical confidence

Maritime: 3σ power measurement at 20m standoff

Nonproliferation applications

Three-lab study of nonproliferation applications for novel neutrino detection technology (LLNL, BNL, LBNL):

- Test site transparency (TST)
- Small modular reactors (SMR)
- AUKUS / Maritime use of nuclear vessels

Approach:

- Analytic calculation of signal rates
- Empirical treatment of cosmogenic backgrounds
- Analytical model for detector response to evaluate signal efficiency and accidental background rates
- Predict precision for a power measurement / sensitivity for signal detection
- *Some potential use cases*
- *May support further development of this technology*

TST: 3σ detection of explosion

Detection of nuclear yield in TNT equivalent

Single day power measurement of a single SMR with 95% statistical confidence

SMR: 2σ power measurement in 1 day, 20 mwe depth

Reactor core power measurements to 99% statistical confidence

Maritime: 3σ power measurement at 20m standoff

Potential impact (nonpro)

Benefits of hybrid technology

- Scalable to large (10s kton) scales
 - Ability to monitor at large standoff distance
 - Sensitivity to weak signals
 - High-fidelity event reconstruction and particle identification
 - High signal efficiency
 - Powerful background rejection
- ➔ Good signal-to-noise ratio, improved sensitivity

Potential impact (nonpro)

Benefits of hybrid technology

- Scalable to large (10s kton) scales
 - Ability to monitor at large standoff distance
 - Sensitivity to weak signals
 - High-fidelity event reconstruction and particle identification
 - High signal efficiency
 - Powerful background rejection
- ➔ Good signal-to-noise ratio, improved sensitivity

Benefits of Eos deployment

- Evaluate event reconstruction capabilities
 - *Future: evaluate particle identification and background rejection capabilities*
 - *Future: measure background rates at / near surface*
 - *Future: direct neutrino detection from a source*
- ➔ Demonstrate potential for surface deployment
- ➔ Cost driver for any future application

Potential impact (science)

Potential impact (science)

Potential impact (science)

Physics program

- **Low-energy (< 5 MeV) Solar vs**
 - No long-lived cosmogenics
 - Naturally neutron-shielding
 - High light-yield for good resolution/low threshold
- **SN Burst and Diffuse SN anti- ν Background**
 - Literally complementary to LAr: anti- ν vs. ν
 - Atmospheric NC rejected via Cher+scint
- **$0\nu\beta\beta$ with natural isotopic (e.g. ^{nat}Te) loading**
 - Beyond tonne-scale at low cost
- **Long-baseline oscillations**
 - Similar CP sensitivity to 10 kt LAr
 - Lighter target, different systematics
 - Very narrow energy resolution

Antinu signal >> nu signal

Require UAr + n shield to achieve this physics in LArTPC DUNE due to intrinsic ³⁹Ar and ⁴²Ar & neutron background

Primary physics goal	Reach	Context
Long-baseline oscillations	$>5\sigma$ for 30% of δ_{CP}	Comparable / complementary to DUNE
Nucleon decay $p \rightarrow \nu K^+$	$T > 3.8 \times 10^{34}$ year	Complementary to DUNE (sensitivity to different modes)
Supernova burst	$< 1(2)^\circ$ pointing 20K(5K) events	Complementary to DUNE (nu vs anti-nu)
Diffuse Supernova Neutrino	5σ	Unique background rejection (deep, Cher+scint ratio)
CNO neutrinos	$< 5(10)\%$	Unique capability, order of magnitude improvement
MSW transition	5σ	Unique capability: depth, low-bkg, low-threshold, PID
Geoneutrinos	$< 7\%$	Only plausible high stats measurement in North America
$0\nu\beta\beta$	$T_{1/2} > 1.1 \times 10^{28}$ year (90%C.L.)	Beyond ton-scale sensitivity